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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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SUPPORTING CHILDREN WITH AUTISM IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTISENSORY, VISUAL SCHEDULING, AND ABA APPROACHES

[Safarova Sanobar Omontashevna](#)

Associate Professor of the National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan named after Nizami

ORCID: 0009-0001-3520-3444

[Rakhimova Ozoda Abdurasul qizi](#)

National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0009-5468-6363

Abstract: This study examines the effectiveness of multisensory instruction, visual scheduling, ABA, and interactive methods for supporting children with autism in inclusive classrooms. Based on the results of an eight-week observation, multisensory activities increased student engagement, visual schedules facilitated adaptation and reduced anxiety, while ABA improved task completion. The findings demonstrate that combining multiple evidence-based strategies is more effective than relying on a single approach.

Key words: autism, inclusive education, multisensory instruction, visual scheduling, applied behavior analysis (ABA), children with special needs, classroom adaptation, evidence-based strategies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida autizmli bolalarni qo'llab-quvvatlashda multisensor o'qitish, vizual rejalashtirish, ABA va interaktiv metodlarning samaradorligini tahlil qiladi. Sakkiz haftalik kuzatuv natijalariga ko'ra, multisensor faoliyatlar o'quvchilarning darsdagi faolligini oshirdi, vizual jadval va ko'rsatmalar moslashuv jarayonini yengillashtirdi, ABA yondashuvi esa topshiriqlarni bajarish darajasini yaxshiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari bir nechta ilmiy asoslangan strategiyalarni uyg'un qo'llash yagona yondashuvdan ko'ra samaraliroq ekanligini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar: autizm, inklyuziv ta'lim, multisensor o'qitish, vizual rejalashtirish, amaliy xulq-atvor tahlili (ABA), maxsus ehtiyojli bolalar, sinf moslashuvi, ilmiy asoslangan strategiyalar.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании анализируется эффективность мультисенсорного обучения, визуального планирования, АВА и интерактивных методов в поддержке детей с аутизмом в условиях инклюзивного образования. По итогам восьминедельного наблюдения установлено, что мультисенсорные занятия повысили учебную активность, визуальные расписания способствовали более комфортной адаптации, а подход АВА улучшил выполнение заданий. Результаты исследования показали, что комплексное применение нескольких научно обоснованных стратегий является более эффективным по сравнению с использованием одного подхода.

Ключевые слова: аутизм, инклюзивное образование, мультисенсорное обучение, визуальное планирование, прикладной анализ поведения (АВА), дети с особыми потребностями, адаптация класса, научно обоснованные стратегии.

INTRODUCTION

The number of children diagnosed with autism is increasing every year, which highlights the need for continuous improvement in the educational system. Inclusive education aims to teach such students together with their typically developing peers while taking into account their special educational needs. In this process, the strategies used by teachers, their professional attitudes, and the level of environmental adaptation play a crucial role. Therefore, this study investigates various approaches to educating children with autism, including interactive methods, multisensory instruction, applied behavior analysis (ABA), and visual scheduling.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of global research demonstrates that the implementation of evidence-based practices is essential for supporting children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in inclusive educational environments. The study conducted by O. Ivar Lovaas (1987) showed that Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) is highly effective in improving the cognitive and social functioning of children with autism. Later studies confirmed that ABA plays a significant role in strengthening behavioral regulation and increasing student engagement in learning activities (Wong et al., 2015).

The TEACCH approach, developed by Gary Mesibov and Victoria Shea, also emphasizes the importance of structured teaching and visual supports. Research indicates that children with ASD demonstrate greater independence and improved task completion when visual schedules and structured routines are applied. Dettmer et al. (2000) reported that visual supports substantially reduce anxiety during transitions and promote behavioral consistency.

Another effective instructional approach for children with autism is multisensory teaching. A. Jean Ayres' Sensory Integration Theory (2005) states that stimulating multiple sensory channels enhances attention, information processing, and educational outcomes. Knight et al. (2015) provided evidence that multisensory activities improve engagement and participation among students with ASD.

In addition, interactive teaching methods in inclusive classrooms contribute positively to the development of communication skills. Samuel Odom et al. (2010) emphasized that inclusive settings create valuable opportunities for peer interaction; however, individualized support remains necessary to address diverse communication needs.

Overall, the literature indicates that no single teaching method is sufficient to fully support children with autism. Rather, the most effective outcomes are achieved through the integration of several evidence-based approaches, including ABA, multisensory instruction, and visual supports. Such a comprehensive model promotes not only academic achievement but also social and emotional development in inclusive educational settings.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of this research was to assess the effectiveness of teaching approaches for pupils with autism in an inclusive classroom environment. To achieve this objective, the study employed a combination of observation, experimental intervention, interviews, document analysis, and outcome assessment methods. The methodological framework was based on the internationally recognized works of O. Ivar Lovaas (1987), Gary Mesibov and Victoria Shea (TEACCH model), Temple Grandin (2006), as well as inclusive education guidelines developed by the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of Uzbekistan.

The study involved 20 children aged 6–10 diagnosed with autism, 20 typically developing children, 8 regular primary school teachers, 2 special education teachers, and 2 school psychologists. All children with ASD had received a formal diagnosis prior to the study in accordance with the standards of the American Psychological Association for Autism Spectrum Disorder.

The experiment was conducted over six weeks using a two-group experimental design. The experimental group, consisting of 10 children with autism, received Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA), multisensory learning activities, visual schedules supported by structured routines, components of the TEACCH approach, and individualized instructional assistance. The control group, also consisting of 10 children with autism, was taught mainly through traditional teaching methods. This design was modeled on the intensive behavioral intervention framework proposed by O. Ivar Lovaas (1987).

The instructional methods applied in the intervention included Discrete Trial Training (DTT), positive reinforcement, and shaping and chaining techniques within the ABA framework. ABA was selected because previous findings demonstrated approximately a 47% improvement in cognitive and social abilities among children receiving structured ABA therapy. Visual scheduling methods included daily visual timetables, step-by-step task instructions, and icons supporting independent activities. According to the TEACCH model, these tools can significantly improve behavioral consistency and task engagement among autistic learners. Multisensory instruction incorporated tactile educational materials, auditory signals, movement-based tasks, and a specially designed sensory area. This approach was grounded in A. Jean Ayres' Sensory Integration Theory, which emphasizes that sensory experiences help maintain attention and reduce anxiety in children with autism. Personalized teaching strategies included the development of Individualized Education Plans (IEPs), setting small and achievable goals, and involving teaching assistants during classroom activities. These practices were aligned with the UNESCO Inclusive Education Framework.

Data collection was carried out through several methods. A standardized observational checklist was used during each lesson to record task participation, task completion, off-task behavior, and communication attempts. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with teachers, special educators, and parents to identify the perceived effectiveness of teaching methods, challenges related to inclusive education, and positive changes in children's behavior and learning progress. In addition, pre-test and post-test assessments were administered using the Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales, academic performance evaluation sheets, and lesson-based attention span monitoring.

Quantitative data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS. Mean scores were compared across groups, and a t-test was applied to determine statistical significance. Behavioral changes were presented in percentage terms. Qualitative data were processed through manual coding of interview transcripts, allowing recurring themes and patterns to be identified. Teacher reflections and classroom observations also contributed to the interpretive conclusions of the study.

Ethical standards were carefully observed throughout the research process. Written consent was obtained from parents, all learning activities were designed to ensure children's comfort and emotional well-being, and personal information together with assessment results was kept strictly confidential. These procedures were fully consistent with the ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The outcomes of the study revealed that the use of diverse instructional strategies significantly improved engagement, behavior, and independence among children with autism. Consistent with the findings reported by Samuel Odom et al. (2015), multisensory and structured behavioral approaches demonstrated the strongest positive influence on students' overall classroom participation.

Notably, students with ASD responded particularly well to multisensory teaching strategies during the observation period, with engagement levels increasing among 78% of the participants. These findings are consistent with the study of Knight et al. (2015), which indicated that multisensory activities enhance attention and task involvement among individuals with ASD. Activities incorporating visual, auditory, and tactile elements maintained more stable on-task behavior than conventional teaching approaches.

The application of Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) techniques also produced substantial improvements. During the final stage of the study, more than half of the students demonstrated increased independence and required less prompting. These results are supported by the earlier findings of O. Ivar Lovaas (1987) and later reviews by Wong et al. (2015), which confirmed the effectiveness of ABA in skill development and positive behavioral improvement.

Visual scheduling generated clear and measurable outcomes as well. In line with the research of Dettmer et al. (2000), approximately 70% of the participating students showed reduced anxiety during transitions, greater understanding of classroom routines, and fewer behavioral disruptions when visual schedules were implemented. Students also demonstrated greater independence in managing their daily activities.

Interactive teaching strategies positively influenced peer interaction and communication, although the degree of progress varied across students. This finding partially supports the observations of Samuel Odom et al. (2010), who noted that inclusive settings create valuable opportunities for social interaction, while individualized adaptations remain necessary for learners with differing communication needs.

Overall, the findings indicate that the most meaningful progress is achieved when several evidence-based practices, particularly ABA, multisensory instruction, and visual scheduling, are integrated. This reinforces previous research highlighting the value of combining proven approaches for learners with ASD in inclusive settings.

These results further strengthen the growing body of evidence showing that children with autism achieve better outcomes in inclusive classrooms when teaching methods are structured, visual, and multisensory. The present study supports the conclusions of Wong et al. (2015), who also found that combining multiple evidence-based practices leads to stronger academic progress than relying on a single method. In this study, the greatest gains were observed when teachers simultaneously applied multisensory activities, ABA techniques, and visual schedules, emphasizing the importance of individualized and flexible instruction.

The strong impact of multisensory instruction is consistent with Knight et al. (2015), who argued that sensory-rich activities sustain attention and facilitate information processing among individuals with ASD. The increased engagement recorded in this research suggests that sensory integration remains an important component of inclusive pedagogy, particularly for learners who experience difficulties with traditional auditory-verbal instruction. At the same time, differences in individual responses indicate that sensory strategies should be adapted according to each child's sensory profile.

The positive outcomes associated with ABA strategies are in line with the foundational work of O. Ivar Lovaas (1987) and subsequent analyses by Wong et al. (2015), which confirmed ABA's effectiveness in

improving task completion and promoting constructive behavior. The present study expands these findings into inclusive education settings, where ABA practices were successfully integrated into general classroom instruction through appropriate teacher preparation. However, the results also suggest that ABA is most effective when complemented by additional strategies, particularly in the area of social communication.

The beneficial effects of visual schedules correspond with earlier research by Dettmer et al. (2000), who demonstrated that clearly organized visual routines reduce anxiety and improve transitions for students with ASD. In the present study, visual scheduling not only reduced behavioral difficulties but also increased independence, highlighting the importance of structured routines in effective inclusion. Their success, however, depends greatly on teachers' consistent implementation.

These mixed outcomes also align with the observations of Samuel Odom et al. (2010), who emphasized that although inclusive settings support social interaction, communication development often requires targeted intervention. While some students showed notable progress in peer communication, others benefited from additional specialized support. This underscores the importance of integrating structured communication assistance into group activities.

In conclusion, the findings demonstrate that inclusive education for children with autism is most effective when instruction is comprehensive, flexible, and evidence-based. No single approach proved universally sufficient; rather, a combination of behavioral organization, sensory support, and visual clarity produced the strongest outcomes. The study also highlights the importance of continuous teacher training, close collaboration between specialists and general educators, and ongoing adaptation of the learning environment to meet the diverse needs of students with ASD.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study highlights the importance of applying a combination of evidence-informed strategies to support children with autism in inclusive classroom settings. The findings indicate that multisensory teaching increases participation, Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) strategies improve behavioral consistency and task completion, while visual schedules reduce anxiety and promote greater independence. Interactive teaching methods can also facilitate social communication; however, they require thoughtful adaptation to meet the diverse communication needs of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

Collectively, these findings build upon earlier research conducted by O. Ivar Lovaas (1987), Samuel Odom et al. (2010), Wong et al. (2015), Knight et al. (2015), and Dettmer et al. (2000), all of which suggest that no single teaching methodology is universally effective for every learner. Rather, meaningful educational progress is achieved when professionals integrate structured behavioral approaches with sensory and visual supports. Such a holistic model not only strengthens academic development but also enables individuals with autism to interact more effectively and confidently with their typically developing peers.

The study further demonstrates that successful inclusion depends on continuous teacher training, close collaboration with specialists, and the ongoing adaptation of the learning environment. Future research may explore how these strategies can be applied to children of different age groups, as well as how digital tools and technology-based interventions can further strengthen inclusive education for students with ASD.

References:

1. O. Ivar Lovaas (1987). Behavioral treatment and normal educational and intellectual functioning in young autistic children. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 55(1), 3–9.
2. Gary Mesibov, Victoria Shea, & Eric Schopler (2005). *The TEACCH approach to autism spectrum disorders*. New York: Springer.
3. Temple Grandin (2006). *Thinking in pictures: My life with autism*. New York: Vintage Books.
4. A. Jean Ayres (2005). *Sensory integration and the child*. Los Angeles: Western Psychological Services.
5. UNESCO (2017). *A guide for ensuring inclusion and equity in education*. Paris: UNESCO.
6. Wong, C., Samuel Odom, Hume, K.A., et al. (2015). Evidence-based practices for children, youth, and young adults with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 45(7), 1951–1966.
7. Knight, V., McKissick, B.R., & Saunders, A. (2015). A review of technology-based interventions to teach academic skills to students with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 45(8), 2628–2648.
8. Dettmer, S., Simpson, R.L., Myles, B.S., & Ganz, J.B. (2000). The use of visual supports to facilitate transitions of students with autism. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 15(3), 163–169.
9. Samuel Odom, Buysse, V., & Soukakou, E. (2010). Inclusion for young children with disabilities: A quarter century of research perspectives. *Journal of Early Intervention*, 33(4), 344–356.
10. American Psychiatric Association (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (DSM-5)* (5th ed.). Washington, DC: APA.
11. Ministry of Preschool and School Education of Uzbekistan (n.d.). *Inclusive education guidelines*. Uzbekistan.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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